

MODERN TOOLS FOR CONTROL AND EVALUATION OF ACHIEVEMENTS OF EDUCATIONAL STANDARDS

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Abstract. *The article deals with the psychological aspects of diagnostics of the master's competence. Ensuring the mastery of the basics of methodological thinking by masters is a necessary prerequisite for the success of subsequent research and practical activities. Diagnosing a master's competence is considered a complex process. As we can see, it is necessary to take into account both pedagogical and psychological components. Therefore, there are still no universal, ready-made tools. There are attempts to measure competence, but mainly they are aimed at measuring ZUN (tests, tasks, questionnaires, etc.).*

Keywords: *psychological aspects, diagnostics, competence, master of ZUN.*

СОВРЕМЕННЫЙ ИНСТРУМЕНТАРИЙ КОНТРОЛЯ И ОЦЕНКИ ДОСТИЖЕНИЙ СТАНДАРТОВ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье рассмотрены психологические аспекты диагностики компетенции магистра. Обеспечение усвоения магистрами основ методологического мышления является необходимой предпосылкой для успешности последующей научно-исследовательской и практической деятельности. Диагностика компетентности магистра считается сложным процессом. Как мы видим, здесь необходимо учитывать как педагогические, так и психологические составляющие. Поэтому до сих пор нет универсальных, готовых инструментов. Есть попытки измерить компетентность, но в основном они направлены на измерение ЗУНов (тесты, задачи, вопросы и т.д.).*

Ключевые слова: *психологические аспекты, диагностика, компетенция, магистр ЗУН.*

The main thing in education is not knowledge itself, but general learning skills: the ability to acquire and effectively use knowledge. Knowledge quickly becomes obsolete or insufficient, which means that it is necessary to master ways to update and replenish it. How the student can apply this knowledge, how competent he is in a broad extracurricular context, his future self-determination depends. The ability to acquire and apply knowledge should include communication skills, skills of self-control and self-assessment, development of creative abilities[1].

An integral part of the learning process is the control of students' knowledge. By definition, control is the ratio of the results achieved to the planned learning objectives. Both the effectiveness of managing the educational process and the quality of training of a school graduate largely depend on its proper organization.

Checking students' knowledge should provide information not only about the correctness or incorrectness of the final result of the activity performed, but also about whether the form of actions corresponds to a given stage of assimilation. Properly set control of students' learning activities allows the teacher to evaluate the knowledge, skills and abilities they receive, provide the necessary assistance in time and achieve the set learning goals. All this together creates favorable conditions for the development of cognitive abilities of students and the activation of their independent work in the classroom. [2]

A well-placed control allows the teacher not only to correctly assess the level of assimilation of the studied material by students, but also to see their own successes and failures. The task of the teacher is to check not only knowledge, but also the elements of practical assimilation of new material by students.

The main goal of controlling knowledge and skills is to identify the achievements, successes of students, to indicate ways to improve, deepen knowledge, skills, in order to create conditions for the subsequent inclusion of students in active creative activity.

This goal is primarily related to determining the quality of assimilation of educational material by students - the level of mastering the knowledge, skills and abilities provided for by the program in the subject.

Secondly, the specification of the main goal of control is associated with teaching schoolchildren the methods of mutual control and self-control, the formation of the need for self-control and mutual control.

Thirdly, this goal involves the education in students of such personality traits as responsibility for the work performed, the manifestation of initiative. [3]

If the listed goals of knowledge and skills control are realized, then we can say that control performs the following functions:

- controlling;
- training;
- diagnostic;
- prognostic;
- developing;
- orientation;
- nurturing.

The controlling function consists in identifying the state of knowledge and skills of students, their level of mental development, in studying the degree of mastering the methods of cognitive activity, the skills of rational educational work.

With the help of control, the initial level for further mastering knowledge, skills and abilities is determined, the depth and volume of their assimilation is studied. The planned is compared with the actual results, the effectiveness of the methods, forms and means of teaching used by the teacher is established.

The learning function of control is to improve knowledge and skills, their systematization. In the process of checking, students check and consolidate the studied material. They not only reproduce previously learned, but also apply knowledge and skills in a new situation. The test helps students to highlight the main thing in the studied material, to make the knowledge and skills being tested clearer and more accurate. Control also contributes to the generalization and systematization of knowledge.

The essence of the diagnostic function of control is to obtain information about errors, shortcomings and gaps in the knowledge and skills of students in the course of mastering educational material, about the number and nature of errors. The results of diagnostic checks help to choose the most intensive teaching methodology, as well as clarify the direction for further improvement of the content of teaching methods and tools. [4]

The predictive function of verification contributes to obtaining advanced information in the educational process. As a result of the check, grounds are obtained for predicting the course

of a certain segment of the educational process: whether specific knowledge, skills and abilities are sufficiently formed to assimilate the next portion of the educational material (section, topic).

The results of the forecast are used to create a model for the further behavior of a student who today makes mistakes of a certain type or has certain problems in the system of methods of cognitive activity.

The forecast helps to get the right conclusions for further planning and implementation of the educational process.

The developing function of control is to stimulate the cognitive activity of students, in the development of their creative abilities. Since in the process of control speech, memory, attention, imagination, will and thinking of students develop. Control has a great influence on the development and manifestation of such personality traits as abilities, inclinations, interests, needs.

The essence of the orienting control function is to obtain information about the degree of achievement of the learning goal by individual students and the group as a whole - how much is learned and how deeply the educational material is studied. Control guides students in their difficulties and achievements. Revealing the gaps, mistakes and shortcomings of students, he shows them the direction of the application of forces to improve knowledge and skills. Control helps the student to get to know himself better, to evaluate his knowledge and capabilities.

The educational function of control is to instill in students a responsible attitude to learning, discipline, accuracy, honesty.

Checking encourages students to more seriously and regularly control themselves when completing assignments. It is a condition for cultivating a strong will, perseverance, and the habit of regular work.

The allocation of the control function emphasizes its role and importance in the learning process. In the educational process, the functions themselves are manifested to varying degrees and in various combinations. The implementation of the selected functions in practice makes control more efficient, and the learning process itself becomes more efficient.

The control must be:

- purposeful,
- objective,
- comprehensive,
- regular,
- individual.

Let's explore these principles of control in more detail.

1) Targeting implies a clear definition of the purpose of each audit. Goal setting determines all further work to justify the forms, types, methods and means of control used.

Control objectives are formed taking into account the answers to the following questions:

- what should be checked,
- who should be interviewed,
- what conclusions can be drawn based on the results of the audit,
- what is the expected effect of the audit.

When concretizing the goals of control, they proceed from the goals of educating, developing and teaching students, which are implemented at this stage of education.

2) The objectivity of control prevents cases of subjective and erroneous judgments that distort the actual performance of students and reduce the educational value of control. The objectivity of control depends on many factors.

Among them are the following:

- clear identification of general and specific learning objectives,
- the validity of the allocation and selection of the content of control,
- availability of methods for processing, analyzing and evaluating the results of control,
- organization of control.

3) The comprehensiveness of control is understood as the coverage of a large content of the material being checked. This principle includes the assimilation of the main ideas of the topic being studied, the assimilation of educational material along certain meaningful, core lines of the topic, and the knowledge by students of individual and significant facts, concepts, patterns, methods of action and methods of activity.

4) Regularity means systematic control, which is combined with the learning process itself.

5) The individuality of control requires an assessment of the knowledge, skills and abilities of each student.

Today, testing, modular and rating systems for assessing the quality of knowledge, quality monitoring, and educational portfolios are used as innovative forms of control.

Testing is one of the most technologically advanced forms of automated control with controlled quality parameters. Tests are applied at all stages of the didactic process. With their help, preliminary, current, thematic, final control of knowledge and skills, accounting for academic performance and educational achievements are effectively provided.

The modular system aims to put students in front of the need for regular academic work throughout the school year.

Rating (from the English "rating") is a certain numerical value, usually expressed on a multi-point scale (for example, 20-point or 100-point) and integrally characterizing the progress and level of knowledge of students in one or more subjects during a certain period learning.

The rating system allows you to overcome many of the shortcomings of the traditional system, and to assess the progress of each student in a fairly differentiated way. The rating system is effective because it:

- takes into account the current progress of the student and thereby significantly activates his independent and uniform work throughout the school year;
- more objectively and accurately assesses the knowledge of students through the use of a fractional 100-point rating scale;
- creates the basis for the differentiation of students, which is especially important in the transition to a multi-level system of education;
- allows you to get detailed information about the progress of knowledge acquisition by each student.

Monitoring in the "teacher-student" system is understood as a set of monitoring and diagnosing measures, determined by the goal-setting of the learning process and providing for the study of the level of assimilation of the material by students in dynamics and its adjustment. Monitoring is a regular monitoring of the quality of knowledge assimilation and the formation of skills in the educational process.

The emergence of the concept of "monitoring" is associated with the formation and development of the information society, which needed objective and subjective information about the state of certain objects and structures. The educational system turned out to be too complex, multifaceted, so that it was possible to immediately create a system that would allow one to objectively judge the state of affairs.

The educational portfolio as an alternative system for assessing students allows solving a number of tasks in building a student-centered educational process: it captures changes and growth over a certain period of time, supports learning goals, encourages the results of students, teachers and parents, reveals the entire range of work performed, ensures the continuity of the learning process from year to year, shows the range of skills and abilities. [5]

Modern tools for monitoring and evaluating the achievements of educational standards make it possible to include evaluation activities in the content of education, help students evaluate and regulate cognitive activity, contribute to changing the style of the teacher's pedagogical activity, create conditions for cooperation between students and classmates and teachers, and contribute to the formation of adequate self-esteem.

The main trend of the last decade is the introduction of standards associated with the assessment system as expected, planned educational achievements or learning outcomes. Moreover, standards of achievement are considered as a mandatory minimum level of achievement.

The task of the teacher is to analyze the proposed approaches to monitoring and evaluating the achievements of education standards and assess the prospects for their application in the course of attestation of students, as well as to build a system for assessing the quality of education in an educational institution. [4,5]

One of the effective tools for managing the quality of education used at the present stage is the monitoring of educational activities, which allows:

1. Make the transition
 - from assessing only learning outcomes to considering the learning process;
 - from a passive answer to a given question to an active construction of the content of the answer;
 - from the assessment of individual, isolated skills to an integrated and interdisciplinary assessment;
 - from attention to metacognition;
 - from changing the concepts of "knowing" and "able" to the application of knowledge and skills, the use of knowledge.
2. In the course of implementation, there is a change in the form of assessment: the transition from a traditional mark to an assessment focused on standards known to students.
3. A change is being made in the nature of the assessment conducted by teachers, self-assessment of students: from a one-time assessment using one measurer (most often a test) to a portfolio (assessment of work performed by students over a certain time).
4. The transition from one-dimensional to multidimensional measurement - from the assessment of only one characteristic of educational achievements to the assessment of several characteristics simultaneously.

5. Transition from the assessment of exclusively individual achievements of students to the assessment of the achievement of a group of students: assessment of the ability to work in a team; evaluation of the results of group work.

By introducing monitoring technology into the educational process, it is possible to effectively manage the quality of education.

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